

Article

Carbon Emissions Disclosure in Indonesia: the Impact of Institutional Ownership

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Dates of submission: 08.05.2024

Date of publication: 28.06.2024

Abstract: *This research aims to determine the effect of institutional ownership on carbon emissions disclosure, with leverage, number of top executives, company age, company size, and profitability as control variables. The sample in the research was non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, but during the research, several companies were eliminated due to incomplete data from 2018-2022. After statistical analysis and modelling, this research found that institutional ownership influences carbon emissions disclosure. In addition, control variables that influence carbon emissions disclosure are the number of top executives, company age, and company size. So the results of this research are in line with the proposed hypothesis. Although this research is limited in the available sample size because not all companies disclose carbon emissions, its novelty lies in the fact that disclosing carbon emissions for all non-financial companies in Indonesia is still an interesting topic to research related to the issue of climate change and global warming.*

Keywords: *carbon emissions disclosure; institutional ownership; greenhouse gas emissions; global warming*

1. Introduction

It has become an international convention to aggressively respond to climate change. Factors that will affect climate change and carbon emission reduction such as population, age structure, gender structure, urbanization, economic development, and industrial restructuring of particular concern (Cook et al., 2019). However, the main cause of global warming is greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, especially companies that engaged in high-carbon industries (He et al., 2021). *Carbon Emission disclosure (CED)* is a form of company contribution and concern for environmental change and is also part of sustainability reporting (Alsaifi et al., 2020). This condition motivates companies to place equal importance on profits but also to be accountable for the environmental damage caused by their manufacturing operations.

Indonesia's greenhouse gas emissions in 2022 will reach 1,240.8 million tons of carbon dioxide (Mt CO₂e) or 1.24 gigatons of carbon dioxide (Gt CO₂e). This figure is equivalent to 2.3% of total global greenhouse gas emissions, making Indonesia the 1st largest emitter in ASEAN, the 3rd largest carbon dioxide contributor in Asia after China and India, and the 6th largest in the world. (Kurnia et al., 2020). Based on Law No. 17/2004 and ratifying the Kyoto Protocol, Indonesia is involved in minimizing

greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, including carbon emissions (Samiaji, 2011). Indonesia has committed to reducing carbon emissions by 26% (approximately 0.67 gigatons) by 2020 (Hardiyansah, Agustini, 2021). As carbon emissions disclosure is still a voluntary disclosure, not all companies disclose the amount of carbon emissions they produce. As a result, there is no confirmation through this regulation (Ratmono et al., 2021). Recognizing the negative potential of GHG emissions, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia continues to make efforts to control the impact early on. Through the Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia Number 7 of 2023, which requires businesses to submit a report on the amount of real GHG emissions they have released at the end of the period. Corporations that disregard these guidelines might be subject to administrative penalties that comply with applicable laws and regulations.

Ikatan Akuntan Indonesia (IAI) regulates the practice of social responsibility disclosure in Indonesia which is regulated in PSAK No. 1 Paragraph 9 indirectly encouraging companies to disclose their environmental responsibilities. Therefore, the disclosure report is not only used by investors but also used by stakeholders. Therefore, it is expected that the company is not only concerned with profits for investors who have trusted to invest their capital, but also the company is expected to care and be responsible for the environment (Budiharta, Kacaribu, 2020). This is because investors are the main stakeholders in business, they encourage the companies they invest in to behave more ethically and consider the impact of climate change on their plans to reduce and increase profitability in the long term (Benlemlih et al., 2023). Under Presidential Regulation No. 61/2011 on the National Action Plan for Greenhouse Gas Reduction, which is yet voluntary, Indonesia has committed itself to reducing carbon emissions. Voluntary social and environmental disclosure is done by many companies to maintain the company's reputation and avoid public rejection. As explained in Article 4, it is stated that business actors contribute to the reduction of GHG emissions. One of the efforts made by companies is by disclosing carbon emissions. However, in Indonesia, carbon emission disclosure in 2018 only reached 5.52%, there was an increase in 2019 to 7.90%, and 13.93% in 2020.

Institutional investors can use several techniques to behave (climate) responsibly, and portfolio adjustments play only a modest part. In a study of worldwide institutional investors on climate risk, 84% of respondents indicated that they had implemented engagement actions related to climate change in the past five years - compared to 29% who sought to reduce their carbon footprint through portfolio changes (Krueger et al., 2020). In this regard, companies in Indonesia also face extensive regulations regarding the reduction of carbon emissions (Rokhmawati, 2021). Carbon emission reporting by business enterprises has been established for around 15 years and is still voluntary; the operations involve two parties (business to business), such as the corporation and the foreign investor (Septyanun et al., 2023). Then with the release of Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 98 of 2021 and Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2 of 2022, carbon emission reporting is mandatory to record and report the implementation of the implementation through the NEK and SRN PPI schemes. The regulation was followed by companies in Indonesia with 48.56% of emissions disclosure in 2021 and 58.59% in 2022.

Previous literature establishes that ownership structure may influence a firm's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) attitudes and behaviors (Pramono et al., 2022). For example, institutional investors such as mutual funds, investment advisers, and individuals have been acknowledged as important stakeholders in the transformation to a green economy (von Schickfus, 2021). Companies in Indonesia are largely controlled by family groups who own many of the top positions and most of the shares. (Qosasi et al., 2022). The connection between carbon disclosure and firm value is also moderately affected by foreign ownership (Muhammad, Aryani, 2021). Our study provides new insights on how institutional ownership influences corporate environmental behavior. Many companies today sacrifice social aspects to address environmental and climate concerns. Given this, our research responds by doing novelty on the role of governance in environmental performance compared to CSR issues in general (Zaman et al., 2022).

Results from studies regarding carbon emissions disclosure are still inconsistent. Previous research by (Alhazaimah et al., 2014) (Ghomi, Leung, 2013) (Halimah, Yanto, 2018) (Kuo et al., 2012) have not found clarity that institutional ownership affects the disclosure of carbon emissions. Meanwhile, research arranged by (Aini et al., 2022) (Benlemlih et al., 2023) (Kiswanto et al., 2023) (Wang et al.,

2019) stated that the implementation of carbon emission disclosure cannot be influenced by management choices based on institutional ownership. According to (Dyck et al., 2019) institutional investors assist companies to perform better in terms of the environment and society, but they do not see any particular risks related to climate policy. As well as research (Azar et al., 2021) shows that companies generally reduce their carbon emissions when the "Big Three" index funds' ownership shares (BlackRock, Vanguard, State Street) increase, in line with data on the engagement actions of these companies. Emissions reductions are expected to improve the competitiveness of companies; however, this is debatable. On the one hand, such reductions are believed to reduce costs due to inefficiencies, but companies require expensive investments that may increase the cost of capital (Rokhmawati, 2021).

The purpose of the current research is to investigate how institutional ownership affects carbon emission disclosure, institutional ownership was chosen as an independent variable because institutional ownership has advantages over individual ownership that is institutional in nature.

2. Stakeholder Theory

According to stakeholder theory, in order for a business to succeed over the long run, it should take into account the concerns of all of its stakeholders, including its workers, clients, suppliers, communities, and shareholders, both society and other parties that can be affected by the policies made by the company (Roberts, 1992) (Suhardjanto et al., 2018). According to (Friedman, 1970), in his article entitled "The Social Responsibility of Business Is to Increase Its Profits" The business owes its stockholders a social duty. The company's objective is to maximize earnings in order to give shareholders a return on their investment, who are considered stakeholders or parties involved in the company's interests.

The aim of the theory of stakeholders is to furnish management with an understanding that stakeholders require environmental and social disclosures in addition to profits (Saadah, n.d.). This will encourage companies to take actions related to environmental management. These days, a variety of interested parties will push businesses to disclose their environmental practices, including investors, consumers, governments, and communities that are conscious of climate change. either directly or indirectly (Depoers et al., 2014).

Stakeholder theory asserts that institutional investors, in their capacity as agents of corporate governance, have an obligation to advance the long-term viability and prosperity of the businesses in which they make investments, as opposed to concentrating only on immediate financial gains (Ingley, Walt, 2004) (How et al., 2014). If a company has diverse shareholdings, this stakeholder theory says that companies should make broader social responsibility disclosures to attract potential shareholders and retain existing shareholders. Since they invest capital in the company, institutional owners who do not have a special relationship with them should also consider the welfare of the company. Therefore, in order to satisfy stakeholder demands, businesses are expected to demonstrate their concern for the environment in their sustainability and annual reports. In the end, stakeholder theory clarifies how stakeholders and businesses are causally related.

The relationship between stakeholder theory and carbon emissions disclosure explains how management realizes stakeholders' expectations. Stakeholder pressure is thought to have a greater impact on managers' perspectives about social and environmental control issues by disclosing carbon emissions. Thus, in this instance, management must strike a balance between competing demands from different stakeholders (Astari et al., 2020).

3. Hypothesis Development

3.1. Institutional Ownership

Institutions such as banks, insurance companies, etc. own shares in companies, known as institutional ownership. If we look at We can observe the benefit of the association between institutional ownership and carbon emissions disclosure: Because institutional ownership gives managers more power over their decisions, agency conflicts between managers and stakeholders can be reduced. Institutional ownership is essential to manage and supervise managers to improve company performance (Krisnawanto, Solikhah, 2019). The more shares owned by institutions in a company, the more

management oversees and controls company performance, especially concerning environmental performance.

Stakeholder theory also discusses the relationship between stakeholders and companies. (Depoers et al., 2014). In this case, management must ensure that all company operations are transparent to stakeholders, especially in terms of carbon emissions disclosure. According to certain studies, institutional ownership influences carbon emission disclosure in a favorable way (Ghomi, Leung, 2013) (Alhazaimeh et al., 2014). It is possible to formulate the following hypothesis based on the findings of earlier research:

Ha: Institutional Ownership Affects the Disclosure of Carbon Emissions

3.2. Carbon Emissions Disclosure

One of the most significant issues faced. We live in a world experiencing global warming. Many of Earth's ecosystems may experience changes due to global warming, such as melting ice that can lead to rising sea levels and extreme climate change and negatively affect human life and living things on Earth. One of the factors contributing to the rise in carbon emissions worldwide is the growing number of businesses that generate carbon gas. Companies are expected to be transparent about their environmental efforts to the public, especially investors. Companies are responsible for disclosing carbon emission information. With transparency, It is anticipated that the general public, and investors in particular, will come to believe more and more that other significant information, including disclosure of carbon emissions, should be taken into account in addition to financial statements (Hapsoro, Falih, 2020).

Figure 1. Framework of the study

4. Research Method

4.1. Data Collection

This research utilizes secondary data and adopts a deductive approach to quantitative research in order to investigate and assess the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The analysis of quantitative data in this research is conducted using secondary data sourced from the annual reports of Indonesian nonfinancial companies listed on the IDX between 2018 and 2022, comprising a total of 797 companies across 10 sectors. The annual report data can be accessed on the IDX website (www.idx.co.id).

4.2. Variables Measurement

4.2.1. Dependent Variable

Carbon Emissions Disclosure

The dependent variable of the research is carbon emission disclosure (CED). CED represents one aspect of corporate environmental responsibility, aimed at aiding governmental initiatives in mitigating carbon emissions and minimizing environmental harm resulting from industrial activities (Kurniawati, Biduri, 2018). The measurement of CED comprises the following items (He et al., 2021).

Table 1. Five items of CED

Item	Detailed Information
I_1	Emission reduction targets and outcomes
I_2	Total operational energy consumption for the reporting period
I_3	Method of carbon emission measurement
I_4	Direct greenhouse gas emissions
I_5	Indirect greenhouse gas energy emissions

The formula employed to compute CED is:

$$CED = \frac{\text{Total items disclosed}}{\text{Total of items}} \quad (1)$$

4.2.2. Independent Variable

Institutional Ownership

Institutional ownership has been selected as the independent variable for this research. The calculation of this variable involves dividing the number of institutional shares by the total number of outstanding shares. Therefore, institutional ownership can be formulated as follows:

$$IO = \frac{\text{Total shares owned by institutions}}{\text{Amount of outstanding shares}} \quad (2)$$

4.2.3. Control Variables

Leverage

Financial leverage serves as a significant indicator reflecting a company's financial risk and the extent to which funds are utilized for external purposes. Prior research has demonstrated that financial leverage impacts CED negatively in firms with higher leverage levels. Leveraged firms might encounter heightened financial strain, potentially leading to less favorable disclosure of carbon emission (Peng et al., 2015) (Ben-Amar, McIlkenny, 2015) (Li et al., 2017). Nevertheless, certain studies indicate that financial leverage does not influence the disclosure of corporate environmental information. In this research, leverage is assessed using the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), formulated as follows:

$$DER = \frac{\text{Total Liability}}{\text{Total Equity}} \quad (3)$$

Total Top Executives

The presence of top executives is not solely accountable for the financial achievements of the company, but they must also possess the capability to make strategic decisions concerning environmental matters attributable to the company's operations (Elsayih et al., 2021). With a significant number of top executives within a company, it is anticipated that a greater amount of information pertaining to carbon emissions will be disclosed (Abdul Majid et al., 2023). Counting the number of audit committee members as stated in the company's annual report enables one to ascertain the quantity of top executives.

Company Age

Lawer and Andreas (2013) state that the age of the company has been computed from its inception. The age of the company indicates its ability to sustain operational activities over time and compete

effectively with other companies. It is closely linked to and influences the financial statements due to its association with the company's growth and development. Companies with a long history are anticipated to offer comprehensive information regarding carbon emissions and the genuine efforts undertaken by the company to mitigate them.

Firm Size

Larger companies possess ample physical and financial resources to diminish carbon emissions through corporate environmental initiatives. Hence, they are frequently deemed capable of implementing sustainability strategies, including the disclosure of carbon emissions (Siddique et al., 2021). The size of a company is determined by its assets; the larger the company, the greater its assets, the greater the assets it has (Shan et al., 2021). The following is the company size formula:

$$SIZE = Ln (Total Assets) \quad (4)$$

Profitability

Companies with strong financial performance are regarded as capable of allocating funds to disclose carbon emissions in greater detail, as this is unlikely to impose a burden on the company (Larasati et al., 2020). The profitability variable in this research utilizes Return on Assets (ROA), which is calculated by dividing the profit after tax by the total assets:

$$ROA = \frac{EBIT}{Total Assets} \quad (5)$$

4.2.4. Data Analysis Technique

In this research, the method of analysis employed was multiple linear regression. The equation for multiple linear regression is as follows:

$$CED = \alpha + \beta1INST + \beta2LEV + \beta3TMTSZ + \beta4AGE + \beta5SIZE + \beta6PROF + \varepsilon \quad (6)$$

Where:

CED = Carbon Emissions Disclosure

α = Constant

$\beta1INST$ = Institutional Ownership

$\beta2LEV$ = Leverage

$\beta3TMTSZ$ = Numbers of Top Executives

$\beta4AGE$ = Company Age

$\beta5SIZE$ = Firms Size

$\beta6PROF$ = Profitability

ε = Error term

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Statistic Descriptive

Table 2. Statistic Descriptive Result

Variables	N	Mean	Std.	Min	Max
CARDIS (Y)	2370	1.583	2.036	0	5
INST	2370	0.542	0.373	0	5.062
LEV	2370	1.091	1.97	-32.5	24.498
PROF	2370	0.114	1.307	-9.483	30.12
TMTSZ	2370	7.9	3.395	0	29
AGE	2370	34.531	18.705	0	106
SIZE	2370	15.853	7.28	0.0259	30.412

The disclosure of carbon emissions among nonfinancial companies listed on the IDX is considerable, as indicated in the table above. Specifically, the results of the descriptive statistical analysis reveal that 58.3% of these companies have disclosed their emissions. Moreover, the average value of the institutional ownership variable stands at 0.542, equivalent to 54.2%, indicating a relatively low percentage of institutional ownership among IDX-listed companies. This research also found that the leverage variable has an average of 1.091, while the profitability variable averages 0.114. Additionally, the average number of top executives is 7.9, representing a mere 7.9 percent, highlighting a limited presence of executive board members. Lastly, the company size variable averages 15,853.

5.2. Regression

5.2.1. Hausman Test

Table 3 Hausman Test Result

<i>Probability</i>	0.0000
<i>A</i>	0.05

The probability value in the Hausman test, as shown above, exceeds the alpha value. Consequently, the fixed effect model emerges as the most suitable choice for this research.

5.2.2. Normality Test

Table 4. Saphiro-Wilk W Test Result

Variable	<i>Skewness</i>
CARDIS	0.00000
INST	0.00000
LEV	0.00000
PROF	0.00000
TMTSZ	0.00000
AGE	0.00000
SIZE	0.00000

Drawing from the outcomes presented in the aforementioned table, the data generated in this research exhibits a normal distribution. Specifically, the skewness values of all variables are below 3 when analyzed through the skewness method. Hence, it is deducible that none of the data utilized in this research encounter normality issues.

5.2.3. Multicollinearity Test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
INST	2.75	0.363271

LEV	1.29	0.773248
PROF	1.01	0.989703
TMTSZ	5.34	0.187119
AGE	4.04	0.247294
SIZE	3.33	0.299883
Mean VIF	2.96	

The table above displays the outcomes of the multicollinearity test subsequent to the centering treatment. The outcomes indicate that the data adheres to the assumption of multicollinearity, namely the Tolerance value ≥ 0.10 and the VIF value ≤ 10 .

5.2.4. Autocorrelation Test

Table 6. Autocorrelation Test

Probability	0.0000
A	0.05

Autocorrelation issues are evident in the regression model of this research, as the probability value in the table above falls below 0.05.

5.2.5. Heteroskedasticity Test

Table 7. Heteroskedasticity Test

Chi ²	1.7
Prob>Chi ²	0.0000

In the table above, the value of 0.0000 is less than 0.05, indicating the presence of heteroscedasticity in this research.

5.2.6. Adjusted R Square Test

Table 8. Adjusted R Square

Overall	0.1240
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Derived from the data analyzed in this research, the Adjusted R Square value stands at 0.1240, equivalent to 12.40%. Consequently, it can be inferred that the capability of the independent variables and control variables in this research to elucidate the dependent variable amounts to 12.40%, whereas 87.60% of the variance is accounted for by variables beyond the scope of this research.

5.2.7. Individual Parameter Significance Test (T-Test)

Table 9. T-Test Result

Variables	Coefficient	t	P > [t]
INST	1.069053	7.36	0.000
LEV	0.264957	10.41	0.158
PROF	0.0040718	0.11	0.913
TMTSZ	0.6505686	35.03	0.000
AGE	0.0428418	2.2	0.028
SIZE	-0.0348124	-2.22	0.027
C	-5.0655088	-7.16	0.000

This test aims to examine the individual impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. Based on the results presented in the table above, with a coefficient of 1.069053 and a probability of 0.0000 (which is less than 0.05), it can be inferred that the hypothesis is supported by the data, revealing a positive and significant correlation between institutional ownership and the disclosure of carbon emissions. The hypothesis testing of the research suggests that companies emphasizing long-term

financial benefits over short-term gains are more inclined to disclose their carbon emissions. These companies bear the responsibility of promoting the long-term sustainability and profitability of the companies in which they invest (Ingley, Walt, 2004) (How et al., 2014).

The coefficient value of the leverage variable, when used as the control variable, is 0.264957 with a probability value of 0.158, which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that there is no significant effect of leverage on the disclosure of carbon emissions.

The variable of profitability, when utilized as the control variable, demonstrates a probability value of 0.913, which exceeds 0.05. The resultant coefficient value is 0.0040718. This indicates that profitability does not have a significant impact on the disclosure of carbon emissions.

The variable representing the number of top executives, when employed as the control variable, exhibits a coefficient value of 0.6505686, with a probability value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This suggests that the number of top executives has a positive and significant influence on the disclosure of carbon emissions.

The variable representing the age of the company, when utilized as the control variable, demonstrates a probability value of 0.028, which is less than 0.05. The resulting coefficient value is 0.0428418, indicating that company age has a positive and significant impact on carbon emissions disclosure.

Similarly, the variable representing the size of the company, when employed as the control variable, yields a probability value of 0.027, also less than 0.05. The coefficient value is 0.0348124, suggesting that company size has a negative and significant effect on carbon emissions disclosure.

5.3. Discussion

Stakeholder theory mandates that organizations consistently prioritize the interests of stakeholders alongside the company's objective of profitability. Among these interests is the availability of both financial and non-financial information, which enhances the company's long-term visibility. In this scenario, the company can showcase its commitment to sustainability.

Regarding the matter of climate change, corporate sustainability is intricately connected to data concerning carbon emissions, which constitute the primary factor driving climate change. The disclosure of carbon emissions information facilitates stakeholders in evaluating the degree to which the company is engaged with and prioritizes this issue.

An entity necessitating such information is the institution. As indicated by the research's results, institutional ownership motivates companies to disclose their carbon emissions. This trend arises because the urge for information dissemination escalates alongside institutional ownership. Regarding the topic of climate change, companies will face mounting pressure to divulge their carbon emissions, which constitute the foremost contributors to the phenomenon.

The outcomes of the research align with the stakeholder theory, which asserts that institutional investors ought to prioritize the long-term sustainability and success of the businesses they invest in, rather than focusing solely on short-term financial gains (How et al., 2014; Ingley, Walt, 2004). It is expected that the increasing presence of institutional investors will encourage more companies in Indonesia to disclose their corporate carbon emissions, thereby elevating the importance of low-carbon awareness for all stakeholders in the long term.

The disclosure of carbon emissions by non-financial enterprises in Indonesia is influenced not only by institutional ownership but also by the age, size, and number of top executives within the company. A higher level of disclosure regarding carbon emissions is likely to be prompted by a larger number of top executives. Similarly, the disclosure of carbon emissions by a corporation tends to increase with its age. This may be attributed to the fact that older companies possess greater experience, thereby placing a stronger emphasis on corporate sustainability. Disclosing carbon emissions is considered a means to achieve sustainability concerning climate change. Furthermore, a larger number of top executives suggests a greater diversity of viewpoints or opinions from individuals who influence the decision-making process regarding carbon emission disclosure, particularly concerning the issue of climate change.

Unlike the other variables, the company size variable solely exerts a negative influence on the disclosure of carbon emissions. Consequently, the probability of a corporation reporting its carbon emissions diminishes as the company size increases. Given the substantial carbon emissions generated by Indonesian businesses, larger enterprises frequently opt not to disclose their carbon emissions to circumvent potential negative publicity.

6. Conclusions, Contributions and Limitations

This research utilizes a sample comprising non-financial companies listed on the IDX from 2018 to 2022 to examine the influence of institutional ownership on carbon emission disclosure. Five control variables are employed to evaluate the impact of disclosing carbon emissions. Our outcomes indicate that institutional ownership significantly and positively affects carbon emission disclosure. Comparable study by (Halimah, Yanto, 2018) shown that institutional ownership has a negative and substantial influence on the disclosure of carbon emissions. Meanwhile, study (Benlemlih et al., 2023) demonstrate how closely institutional ownership varies with GHG emission levels. Overall, our findings point to the need for institutional investors to meet low-GHG emission investing objectives.

Based on empirical data, we propose several practical implications. Firstly, our statistical results reveal that the proportion of companies disclosing carbon emissions is lower than the entire sample, suggesting a potential need for a carbon emissions disclosure policy by the government of Indonesia. Secondly, institutional ownership might incentivize companies to disclose carbon emissions, offering Indonesian companies the opportunity to increase their institutional ownership share. Moreover, we recommend that future research compares the implementation of carbon emission disclosure before and after the enactment of Republic of Indonesia Presidential Regulation Number 98 of 2021 and Republic of Indonesia Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation Number 2 of 2022. This comparative analysis would provide insights into how businesses responded to these regulations regarding carbon emission disclosure.

Like any empirical research, this research has limitations. The carbon emissions disclosure index utilized in this research may not encompass all data that accurately represents the quality of carbon emissions disclosure. It is hoped that future studies may address this weakness by incorporating additional data.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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